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NITROUS OXIDE FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF LABOR

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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By

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ABSTRACT

The physiologic process of pain in a parturient is multifaceted and can be altered by multiple factors such as prior labor experience, anxiety level, and fear of loss of autonomy. As healthcare providers it is critical to ensure that the access to various approaches of labor analgesia are available to parturients. Many facilities that employ multiple options for parturients have demonstrated improved postpartum maternal satisfaction, self-esteem, and outlook on the newborn. At present, nitrous oxide is becoming increasingly popular in facilities throughout the United States. This literature review describes the knowledge deficit which exists within healthcare facilities which may discourage healthcare staff from offering nitrous oxide. Many facilities lack standardized protocols or references which can promote confidence in healthcare providers offering analgesic techniques such as nitrous oxide. Therefore, this clinical reference has been created in hopes to assist and provide a brief introduction to the topic of nitrous oxide for labor pain management.

Keywords: labor analgesic, labor analgesic adjuncts, efficacy of nitrous oxide, parturient satisfaction, clinical reference, safety of nitrous oxide, self-administration practices of nitrous oxide, screening and contraindications of nitrous oxide, parturients

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BACKGROUND

Childbirth is a multifaceted experience that plays a critical role in postpartum maternal satisfaction, self-esteem, and outlook on the newborn (Declercq et al., 2014). This experience is influenced by factors such as prior experience with labor pain, anxiety level, fear and desired level of autonomy (Declercq et al., 2014; Vedam et al., 2019). Inadequate management of these factors can contribute to decreased overall satisfaction with the labor experience. Evidence suggests multimodal management of pain can alleviate anxiety and improve patient satisfaction (Dammer et al., 2014; Houser et al., 2019; Richardson et al., 2019).

Problem Statement

Currently, the gold standard for the management of labor analgesia is neuraxial anesthesia, which can be administered in the form of an epidural, spinal, caudal, or combined spinal-epidural (Sng & Sia, 2017). This method of labor analgesia is effective but might not always be advantageous for laboring women. Unfavorable circumstances with this method of analgesia may be encountered when hospitals lack sufficient resources such as an on-call anesthesia provider to promptly administer the neuraxial block. As a result, laboring women are exposed to prolonged wait times which leads to increased pain, anxiety and dissatisfaction with the labor experience (Attanasio et al., 2015). Additional disadvantages associated with neuraxial analgesia, include risk for temporary paralysis of the lower extremities which restricts birthing positions and mobility. This can contribute to a decreased sense of control, which in turn affects laboring women's satisfaction with the labor experience (Collins, 2015). Furthermore, the displacement of an indwelling epidural catheter is always a concern with this method of analgesia (Collins, 2015). Importantly, neuraxial anesthesia may not be an option for laboring

women who have hypovolemia, indeterminate neurologic disease, infection at the insertion site, coagulopathy, and increased intracranial pressure (Schrock & Harraway-Smith, 2012).

Another frequently used pain management intervention is the use of systemic opioid analgesia such as morphine, nalbuphine, and fentanyl. A major risk associated with opioids' use during labor is neonatal respiratory depression due to the drugs' ability to cross the placenta (Phillips et al., 2017). Maternal adverse effects of opioids include drowsiness, nausea, vomiting, and pruritus (Smith et al., 2018). Besides these risks, systemic opioids were also found to provide only moderate satisfaction with labor pain management (Smith et al., 2018). At present, more laboring women desire to have more control over their birthing experience. For these women, neuraxial analgesia and opioids may not be an option due to their autonomy restricting effects (Richardson et al., 2019). Despite having moderate pain levels, high levels of satisfaction have been shown with the use of less invasive opioid-free labor interventions (Berlit et al., 2013; Richardson et al., 2017b).

One strategy that has been suggested to alleviate labor pain and reduce anxiety while maintaining autonomy is the use of nitrous oxide. In the U.S., high concentrations of nitrous oxide were widely used for labor during the 1950s and 1960s but faded from practice with the emergence of neuraxial/regional anesthesia (Collins et al., 2018). In 2012, self-administering nitrous oxide devices were approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for labor-management at a maximum concentration of a 50/50 gaseous mixture of nitrous oxide and oxygen (Collins, 2015; Collins et al., 2012; Pinyan et al., 2017). At this low concentration nitrous oxide works as a safe anxiolytic and analgesic. However, it is not a strong analgesic, and therefore is not intended to provide equivalent analgesia when compared to an epidural. Despite this, women have reported diminished pain and less anxiety when using nitrous oxide throughout

the different stages of labor (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, 2012; Likis et al., 2014; Richardson et al., 2019).

Following FDA approval, nitrous oxide use during labor has been gaining popularity and is now offered in over 500 hospitals and birth care centers across the U.S. (Richardson et al., 2019). Currently, 50/50 nitrous oxide is not offered to laboring women receiving obstetrical care in the Kaiser Permanente of Southern California (KP SCAL) facilities. Internal data gathered from KP SCAL facilities demonstrates that nitrous oxide has been requested for labor management among their patients. In an effort to provide evidence-based patient-centered care, KP SCAL strives to improve patient satisfaction with the laboring experience by providing nitrous oxide. Multiple barriers have been identified in quality improvement projects when implementing nitrous oxide within hospitals with the most common factors consisting of lack of staff education and misconceptions of safety among employees. Therefore, prior to initiating a protocol, a clinical reference must be in place for staff to adequately understand the appropriate utilization of nitrous oxide during labor. Currently, there is no clinical reference in place for self-administration of nitrous oxide in KP SCAL facilities. The utilization of nitrous oxide self-administration will become part of KP SCAL facilities in the near future due to patient demand for alternate options of labor analgesia.

Purpose Statement

Therefore, the purpose of this project was to create reference material on nitrous oxide for labor-management to facilitate the subsequent implementation of this intervention at KP SCAL facilities. The two aims were to: develop a Southern California Permanente Medical Group (SCPMG) regionally approved clinical reference for KP SCAL obstetrical staff on the use

of nitrous oxide during labor, and gain approval to publish the clinical reference on KP SCAL Clinical Library website.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Synthesis of Literature

A literature search was performed using PubMed, CINAHL, OVID, Cochrane Library, and Google Scholar databases. Search terms for labor pain management were: “nitrous oxide,” “Nitronox,” “Entonox,” “labor,” “labor pain,” “labor experience,” “labor pain management,” “anxiety,” “labor analgesia,” and “maternal satisfaction.” Search terms regarding contraindications, safety, and administration were: “nitrous oxide,” “nitrous oxide safety,” “occupational exposure,” “safety and risk,” “administration method,” and “protocol implementation.” The search was limited to peer-reviewed articles published in the English language. Articles that were older than ten years were excluded, unless a seminal publication, along with comparison groups utilizing volatile agents or medications no longer being utilized for labor management. The references from retrieved articles were also examined for further relevant articles. The overall topics for the review of literature were: (a) labor pain and experience, (b) current labor-management interventions, (c) nitrous oxide utilization, (d) equipment for nitrous oxide utilization, (e) safety with the utilization of nitrous oxide, and (f) implementation of nitrous oxide.

Effects of Pain, Anxiety, and Autonomy on the Labor Experience

Various factors influence the labor experience, including pain, anxiety, and autonomy. Adequate management of pain helps mitigate both physiological and psychological stress related to labor. Pain can evoke a neuroendocrine stress response resulting in increased oxygen consumption, hyperventilation, increased cardiac output, and ineffective contractions (Brownridge, 1995). In a longitudinal study, Garthus-Niegel et al. (2014) found pain to have a

substantially detrimental effect on the overall labor experience and to be associated with the development of post-traumatic stress symptoms.

The perception of pain can be determined by anxiety and fear, as described by Read in the fear-tension-pain cycle (as cited in Jones et al., 2012). This philosophy of pain suggests that muscle tension is a product of anxiety and fear, thereby causing an increased perception of pain. Decreasing these two variables can break this cycle. Two studies supporting this theory demonstrated a statistically significant association between anxiety and increased self-rated pain before labor analgesia (Floris & Irion, 2015; Pettersson et al., 2016). Addressing these variables, Collins (2015) found a pain relief intervention with anxiolytic properties (nitrous oxide) to diminish anxiety and fear of childbirth. Despite the influence of pain on the labor experience, Richardson et al. (2017b) revealed other contributors to maternal satisfaction on childbirth, such as cognitive, emotional, and physical domains.

Current literature supports autonomy as a factor of a positive labor experience (Richardson et al., 2019). Attanasio et al. (2014) showed that the laboring woman's perception of shared decision-making and communication among clinicians related to coordinating care to be associated with improved labor experiences. Furthermore, personal control during labor was found to be a strong determinant of overall satisfaction with childbirth (Richardson et al., 2017b). In a qualitative study, autonomy and control of decision making were again found to be positive influences on the labor process (Richardson et al., 2019). The labor process is a complex and subjective experience that is highly individualized (Lowe, 2002). Therefore, a variety of approaches to promote comfort and pain relief are necessary to improve the labor experience.

Current Labor Pain Interventions in the United States

In the U.S., epidural analgesia (EA) is the most common intervention for labor pain relief (Hellams et al., 2018; Nodine et al., 2020). Despite EA being the most effective method, there are also many shortcomings to this type of analgesic (Jones et al., 2012). As stated above, EA has a longer onset of action (30 minutes) in comparison to nitrous oxide (30-50 seconds) and intravenous opioids (5 minutes) (Hellams et al., 2018). Moreover, EA is required to be administered by an anesthesia provider, so there can be a lag in administration time based on provider availability (Attanasio et al., 2015). This analgesic is not an option if contraindicated or rejected by the laboring woman for reasons stated above.

Systemic opioids, specifically parenteral opioids, are also frequently used for pain management during labor (Anderson, 2011). As discussed, opioids cross the placental barrier resulting in reduced fetal heart rate, respiratory depression, a suppressed central nervous system, along with a decreased ability to breastfeed (Hellams et al., 2018; Nodine et al., 2020). Furthermore, a Cochrane study showed insufficient evidence supporting the effectiveness of parenteral opioids (Jones et al., 2012). In another study, systemic opioids were found to provide minimal to moderate pain relief during labor and became less effective in the transition phase of labor (Anderson, 2011). Adverse effects of this type of analgesic were sedation, nausea/vomiting, decreased gastric motility, urinary retention, and respiratory depression (Anderson, 2011).

There are a variety of additional pharmacological and non-pharmacological techniques for labor pain relief. Other pharmacological interventions include nitrous oxide, local anesthetic nerve blocks, and non-opioid drugs. Alternative methods reported to improve the laboring experience include immersion in water, relaxation, acupuncture, massage, and distraction therapy

(Jones et al., 2012). In a Cochrane study, nitrous oxide and epidurals were the only interventions deemed as effective labor pain relieving methods (Jones et al., 2012). Unlike other pharmacological options, nitrous oxide has demonstrated effectiveness in providing anxiolysis (Hellams et al., 2018).

Nitrous Oxide Utilization During Labor

Overview and Current Practice

As an odorless, tasteless, and nonflammable inhalational gas, nitrous oxide has an established history in its use as an anesthetic, analgesic, and anxiolytic agent (Collins et al., 2018). Commonly referred to as “laughing gas,” nitrous oxide is frequently used to provide pain relief during surgical and dental procedures in the U.S.

For surgical anesthesia in the U.S., nitrous oxide is commonly used as a low potency inhalational anesthetic. In such cases, nitrous oxide increases the uptake of a secondary inhalational anesthetic thereby reducing induction time by way of what is known as the “second gas effect” (Collins et al., 2018). In cases where higher concentrations are utilized, 65-70% of nitrous oxide allows for the gas to produce anesthetic effects, including loss of consciousness, while simultaneously providing analgesia and anxiolysis. The combination of these effects contribute to a reduction of anesthetic agents and narcotics required by patients under general anesthesia during surgery (Collins et al., 2018).

In developed countries outside the U.S., subanesthetic nitrous oxide concentrations of 30-50% have been successfully utilized as a less invasive option for the management of pain and anxiety experienced during the laboring process. At this low concentration, parturients are able to maintain alertness, as well as sustain motor and sensory function, while experiencing a diminished perception of pain, improved relaxation and decreased stress levels (Hellams et al.,

2018; Illuzzi et al., 2018). All of these factors contribute to women having more sense of control over their laboring experience resulting in an increase in overall patient satisfaction. Parturient self-administration of 50/50 mixture of nitrous oxide and oxygen for labor analgesia was first introduced in England in 1934 and has since remained popular among European laboring women (Collins et al., 2018). It is estimated that up to 75% of parturients in the United Kingdom, Australia, New Zealand, Finland, and Canada use nitrous oxide during labor (Collins et al., 2018; Likis et al., 2014; Pinyan et al., 2017).

The successful utilization of nitrous oxide in labor and delivery units abroad has influenced its usage in the U.S. as implementation has increased by seven-fold in the last four years (Collins, 2015; Richardson et al., 2019). Professional organizations such as the American College of Nurse-Midwives and the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists have both endorsed the use of nitrous oxide as an adjunct for parturients who desire more control over their birthing experience (Collins, 2015; Collins et al., 2012; Pinyan et al., 2017).

Mechanism of Action

While the utilization of nitrous oxide is well documented, the mechanism of action is multifactorial and is not entirely understood. At high concentrations, greater than 50%, it is believed that nitrous oxide produces anesthetic effects predominantly by inhibition of N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) excitatory glutamate receptors in the brain. (Collins et al., 2018; Emmanouil & Quock, 2007). At subanesthetic concentrations, 30% to 50%, analgesic and anxiolytic effects without unconsciousness are demonstrated (Emmanouil & Quock, 2007).

The mild analgesic action of nitrous oxide is thought to be due to the endogenous release of opioid peptides known as enkephalins, which bind to opioid receptors in the midbrain and stimulate the descending pathways to modulate painful stimuli in the brain and spinal cord

(Becker & Rosenberg, 2008; Collins et al., 2018; Emmanouil & Quock, 2007). Furthermore, the release of corticotropins, dopamine and norepinephrine are also hypothesized to play a role in the analgesic effects of nitrous oxide. Studies have shown that nitrous oxide increases the release of dopamine and norepinephrine in the central nervous system resulting in decreased pain perception (Collins et al., 2018; Illuzzi et al., 2018). The NMDA receptor antagonism seen with nitrous oxide may also play a role in the prevention of hyperalgesia associated with chronic pain syndrome (Collins et al., 2012). Evidence suggests that the analgesic efficacy of 30% nitrous oxide concentration is equivalent to 10-15 mg of intravenous morphine (Becker & Rosenberg, 2008; Emmanouil & Quock, 2007).

Anxiolysis and sedation, similar to the effects seen with benzodiazepines, are also demonstrated at subanesthetic concentrations of nitrous oxide. These anxiolytic effects are believed to be mediated by γ -aminobutyric acid receptors (GABA) and NMDA receptor inhibition. NMDA inhibition, similar to that of the drug Ketamine, is likely to explain the weak dissociative effect of nitrous oxide (Starr & Baysinger, 2013; Richardson et al., 2017a). This effect enables the parturient to feel a sense of detachment and a decrease in pain perception yet, still being aware that the pain is present (Hellams et al., 2018; Illuzzi et al., 2018).

Self-Administration and Equipment Utilized

Parturient self-administration remains the current practice for the delivery of nitrous oxide, where FDA-approved devices provide users direct control of delivery. The most popular of these devices for labor analgesia is the Nitronox machine, supplied by Porter Instruments (Collins et al., 2018). This apparatus utilizes a blender device that combines nitrous oxide and oxygen sources to be delivered at a fixed concentration of 50% nitrous oxide (Collins et al., 2018; Starr & Baysinger, 2013). Once prepared for delivery, the nitrous oxide is delivered via a

handheld face mask. A tight seal is created as the parturient places the mask over the nose and mouth. Upon inhalation, a negative pressure demand valve is triggered, releasing the blend of gases to the parturient (Collins et al., 2012; Hellams et al., 2018; Pinyan et al., 2017). The low solubility of nitrous oxide provides rapid uptake of the gas as parturients experience maximum analgesic effectiveness within 30 to 50 seconds (Collins et al., 2012; Illuzzi et al., 2018).

Intermittent inhalation in practice is known as the most superior method of self-administration (Collins et al., 2018; Pinyan et al., 2017). Starting approximately 30 seconds before the onset of contractions, this method allows for the parturient to receive maximum analgesic effectiveness during the peak of uterine contraction. Literature supports that parturients experience the most significant relief when using the intermittent method along with experiencing fewer adverse side effects such as dizziness, dysphoria, or nausea (Collins et al., 2018; Collins et al., 2012).

Following the cessation of contraction, the parturient is instructed to exhale back into the mask so that the gaseous waste is eliminated via the scavenging system (Collins, 2015). If at any point during self-administration the parturient becomes sedated or too drowsy to hold the mask independently, the flow of gas terminates as there is no longer a tight mask seal. Because of its low solubility, nitrous oxide has a fast offset and upon exhalation is quickly eliminated from the body in just a few minutes (Collins et al., 2018; Starr & Baysinger, 2013). Once the parturient recovers and is able to independently place the mask over her face, the inhalational force will, once again, trigger the release of gas. An important consideration with self-administration of nitrous oxide is that only the parturient is allowed to hold the face mask over her face and should not receive assistance if she is too drowsy to achieve this task independently (Collins et al., 2018; Nodine et al., 2020; Pinyan et al., 2017).

Efficacy of Nitrous Oxide: Pain, Anxiolytic and Patient Satisfaction

Labor pain is a subjective experience felt only by the parturient. Although evidence suggests nitrous oxide as being a weak analgesic when administered at subanesthetic doses, additional effects such as anxiolysis and parturient autonomy provide a positive birth experience in the laboring woman (Hellams et al., 2018; Richardson et al., 2017b; Richardson et al., 2019). Most outcomes analyzed regarding the efficacy of pain relief with nitrous oxide during labor are identified in studies utilizing the visual analog scale (VAS) or numerical rating scale (NRS). A recent systematic review published in the U.S. on the management of labor pain with nitrous oxide examined 58 articles based on studies conducted in English with the primary outcomes of patient satisfaction and efficacy of pain relief. Efficacy of pain relief was examined in 21 studies of which only four were of fair quality. Outcomes from individual studies utilized different comparison groups and demonstrated great variability in the efficacy of pain relief, thereby making it difficult to synthesize. Furthermore, several studies utilized nitrous oxide in higher concentrations than currently administered for labor pain thus making it difficult to compare to current practice. Studies that demonstrated low levels of efficacy often compared nitrous oxide's pain relief to that of an epidural, which is the gold standard of labor pain relief. However, in some parturients, nitrous oxide was demonstrated to be an effective pain management option for those who were unable or did not wish to have an epidural. Results from this systematic review ultimately established the limited number of good quality studies that exist regarding nitrous oxides efficacy on labor pain management (Likis et al., 2014).

Another systematic review published in Iran contained 14 articles with primary outcomes consisting of the efficacy of pain relief and satisfaction rate. Results from this study demonstrated a statistically significant difference in the mean pain relief score indicating that

nitrous oxide provided better pain relief than the comparison group (Sheyklo et al., 2017).

However, it should be noted that studies utilized in this systematic review contained comparison groups predominantly with no intervention. Since parturient expectations regarding pain and satisfaction vary widely in other countries results obtained from this systematic review cannot easily be generalized to the U.S.

An observational study conducted by Dammer et al. (2014) demonstrated a statistically significant decrease in pain NRS when comparing pain score pre and post utilization of nitrous oxide during labor. Furthermore, it was revealed that a mother's experience during expulsion and bearing down stage was also improved with nitrous oxide. Pinyan et al. (2017) revealed similar findings with an average three-point reduction on NRS of labor pain after initiation of nitrous oxide. While nitrous oxide did not relieve pain during the third stage of labor, it was found to be primarily efficacious during the first and second stages of labor. In addition, a quality improvement study Illuzzi et al. (2018) revealed that following implementation of nitrous oxide at Yale-New Haven Hospital a slight decrease in epidural rates and a decrease in overall use of narcotics were reported. Overall, studies regarding the efficacy of nitrous oxide for the management of labor pain are limited, but still, demonstrate its weak analgesic effect. Analgesic effects when utilizing nitrous oxide are especially evident when compared with no intervention (Naddoni et al., 2016; Parsa et al., 2017). Positive outcomes concerning the efficacy of pain relief in studies appear to be based on nitrous oxide's ability to meet the parturient's preconceived goals for labor rather than completely abolishing pain (Nodine et al., 2020; Richardson et al., 2017b). Therefore, to better understand the efficacy of nitrous oxide utilization during labor it appears to be more pertinent to examine outcomes concerning laboring women's satisfaction with the birth experience.

Multiple individual studies including a systematic review regarding labor-management addressed parturient satisfaction with nitrous oxide administration. Studies analyzed satisfaction levels of parturients through various measures which included descriptive questionnaires, satisfaction rating scores, and the likelihood to utilize nitrous oxide in future labors. A systematic review of four studies that analyzed patient satisfaction revealed a higher satisfaction rate with the utilization of nitrous oxide against the comparison group (Sheyklo et al., 2017). It must be noted that three of these studies utilized no intervention as comparison groups and one study utilized Meperidine. Results from these studies may not be easily generalized to other populations due to cultural differences in labor experiences and satisfaction.

Multiple studies revealed high satisfaction with the utilization of nitrous oxide (Houser et al., 2019; Richardson et al., 2017a; Richardson et al., 2019; Rivas et al., 2018; Zanardo et al., 2018). Richardson et al. (2017b) identified that parturients who received solely nitrous oxide for labor analgesia reported high overall satisfaction scores when compared to those receiving only neuraxial analgesia (OR 2.5; 95% CI 1.4-4.6; P= 0.002). Interestingly, a subsequent study revealed high satisfaction scores in 90% of parturients despite only 36% rating the analgesic effectiveness of nitrous oxide as high (Richardson et al., 2019). This illustrates the multifactorial effectiveness with the utilization of nitrous oxide during the laboring process.

Supporting the findings related to patient satisfaction, three studies found that the majority of parturients having used nitrous oxide would utilize nitrous oxide for future labors (Dammer et al., 2014; Houser et al., 2019; Zanardo et al., 2018). Additionally, Dammer et al. (2014) identified influential factors affecting the decision to use nitrous again, including the timing of nitrous oxide inhaled, how well the women tolerated the medication, and the age of the parturients.

Although positive outcomes were demonstrated with nitrous oxide utilization, unfavorable side effects were also reported. Side effects of nitrous oxide were demonstrated to be dose-dependent in which the subanesthetic doses utilized for labor analgesia were shown to be mild (Dammer et al, 2014; Illuzi et al., 2018; Likis et al, 2014; Pasha et al., 2012; Pinyan et al., 2017). Several studies reported nausea as the most common side effect of nitrous oxide during labor followed by dizziness and drowsiness (Dammer et al. 2014; Illuzi et al., 2018; Likis et al., 2014; Pinyan et al., 2017). Likis et al. (2014) analyzed the maternal adverse effects of nausea and vomiting in 32 studies demonstrating rates ranging from 0-45%. However, the increasingly higher rates in certain studies were demonstrated in those utilizing concentrations of nitrous oxide greater than 50%. Only one study by Pasha et al. (2012) had contrasting results in which the most common side effect was mouth dryness followed by headache and dizziness with nausea and vomiting being less common. This appeared to be dependent on variables such as whether the delivery of nitrous oxide by a parturient was continuous or intermittent throughout stages of labor. In addition, all maternal side effects were well tolerated by parturients and shown to be reversible upon treatment and discontinuation of nitrous oxide.

Taken together, evidence suggests that nitrous oxide may not be effective in every case of labor pain management; nevertheless, it may be more effective in women desiring a more natural birthing experience and less invasive pain management strategies. Important factors with nitrous oxide self-administration such as degree of mobility and autonomy promote a greater degree of empowerment and result in improved parturient satisfaction. Rather than being seen as a replacement for epidurals, nitrous oxide can be recognized as a substitute to utilizing narcotics, an adjunct to nonpharmacologic methods of labor-management, or assist with the transition to neuraxial anesthesia. Now that nitrous oxide is becoming increasingly popular in hospitals in the

U.S., more research can be undertaken to better understand the efficacy, patient satisfaction, and adverse effects related to its use.

Safety of Nitrous Oxide Exposure

Safety concerns from exposure to nitrous oxide originate from evidence which demonstrates its impairment of metabolic pathways and Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) synthesis potentially causing genetic and protein abnormalities (Sanders et al., 2008). These effects identify nitrous oxide as possibly being neural toxic and teratogenic, however, duration and concentrations administered for this effect are higher than those utilized for labor analgesia (Rooks, 2011). Neurotoxic effects associated with nitrous oxide are theorized to be dependent on periods of exposure where a fetus is more vulnerable specifically during neural synaptogenesis. Nevertheless, limitations exist from the examination of only non-human subjects where only educated assumptions can be made correlating safety with concentration and length of administration (Collins et al., 2012; Savage & Ma, 2014; Vallejo & Zakowski, 2019).

At present, what is known about safe administration of nitrous oxide use for labor analgesia demonstrates minimal toxicity and depression of the cardiovascular system in laboring women (Rooks, 2011). Even though nitrous oxide crosses the placenta it is not metabolized in fetal or maternal tissue and, therefore, central nervous system and respiratory depression are not seen in neonates after birth due to rapid elimination with the initiation of respirations (Collins et al., 2018). In addition, studies have demonstrated no effect on Apgar and neurobehavioral scores of neonates, as well as, fetal heart rate from its utilization (Earhart et al., 2019; Likis et al. 2014; Nodine et al., 2020; Rooks, 2011).

Concerns regarding healthcare occupational exposure to nitrous oxide primarily surrounds the reproductive risk of the individual caring for the parturient. The current U.S.

standard exposure limit for healthcare workers recommended by the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health defines a set 8 hour limit of 25 parts per million (Vallejo & Zakowski, 2019). Evidence regarding the effects of occupational exposure for healthcare workers is limited because many studies were performed prior to modern scavenging techniques and were studied in areas where high concentrations and no scavenging was utilized (Rooks, 2011; Van Der Kooy, 2012; Wrońska-Nofer et al, 2012). Caution on the interpretation of these studies should be made taking into account the current modernization of equipment that includes scavenging systems on devices. In addition, healthcare workers are trained to educate the mothers of the importance of exhaling back into the mask (Vallejo & Zakowski, 2019; Van Der Kooy, 2012). Currently, there is no evidence connecting self-administered nitrous oxide in the labor setting to reproductive risk while scavenging equipment is utilized. However, few studies exist that have demonstrated elevated occupational exposure limits despite proper scavenging systems. In these instances, the reasons were primarily due to mothers failing to exhale back into the mask, a poor mask fit, and improper ventilation systems on units (Vallejo & Zakowski, 2019; Van Der Kooy, 2012; Rooks, 2011). This stresses the importance of providing adequate education and training to the bedside nurse as well as laboring mothers to ensure adherence to additional guidelines in reducing exposure.

Taken together, studies have demonstrated adequate safety with the utilization of nitrous oxide for labor analgesia on mother, fetus, and neonate. However, more research is needed on the occupational risk of healthcare workers in well-ventilated labor and delivery units with scavenging systems. In addition, further research must be done to better understand the adequate number of exhalations parturients must provide into the mask to adequately eliminate gas. For

these reasons, studies are ongoing involving nitrous oxide's safety risk of exposure for mothers, newborns, and healthcare workers as utilization is becoming increasingly popular.

Screening and Contraindications to Use of Nitrous Oxide

Screening of parturients prior to the administration of nitrous oxide is essential to rule out any contraindications and ensure its safe administration. Factors that determine whether a patient is an appropriate candidate for the utilization of nitrous oxide involve examining relative and absolute contraindications and evaluating the risks versus benefits to the parturient. One of the initial factors to assess for nitrous oxide utilization is the patient's ability to adequately hold a face mask for self-administration (Collins, 2015). This may be a problem for women who struggle with claustrophobia or have impaired mental status required for adequate mask seal since mask straps cannot be used. In addition, because nitrous oxide elimination is through the lungs, it is not recommended for patients with severe lung diseases as it requires adequate oxygenation. Due to nitrous oxide's interference with cobalamin, it should be avoided in parturients who are at increased risk for vitamin B12 deficiency (Richardson et al., 2017a). Lastly, because nitrous oxide is known to easily diffuse in and expand air spaces it should not be used in any patient diagnosed with abnormal air-containing cavities (Lew et al., 2018).

Barriers and Facilitators to the use of Nitrous Oxide During Labor

Despite the evidence surrounding the efficacy and increased patient satisfaction of nitrous oxide during labor, the identification of barriers and facilitators is pertinent to a successful implementation of any new intervention. Due to the recent popularity of nitrous oxide, current literature discusses the development of a written policy and procedure guideline for future implementation of nitrous oxide for laboring women (Migliaccio et al., 2017). Barriers identified include lack of staff compliance and poor staff education (Houser et al., 2019). Starr and

Baysinger (2013) further discuss the lack of suitable equipment and provider unfamiliarity with the techniques as barriers to implementation in the United States. Multiple articles support the need for a thorough education on nitrous oxide for the nursing staff as well as the interdisciplinary team (Illuzzi et al., 2018; Migliaccio et al., 2017; Pinyan et al., 2017). Two of these facilities discussed having training from the vendor, as well as a required competency (Migliaccio et al., 2017; Pinyan et al., 2017).

Additionally, Pinyan et al. (2017) implemented a nurse-driven model due to the lack of full-time obstetrical anesthesia coverage. A nurse-driven model means the bedside nurse can set up and administer nitrous oxide to laboring women. This model promotes the use of nitrous oxide and provides laboring women with an alternative option for pain relief (Pinyan et al., 2017). Nitrous oxide, as the alternative labor analgesic, was seen to decrease the use of narcotics, increase mobility, and promote participation during labor.

The development of the policy and procedure guidelines involves the approval of multiple hospital departments and executive committees (Migliaccio et al., 2017; Pinyan et al., 2017). Therefore, obtaining buy-in from stakeholders will facilitate the approval process (Pinyan et al., 2017). Buy-in strategies, such as sharing literature and vendor information with stakeholders, are meant to increase understanding and support of nitrous oxide during labor (Migliaccio et al., 2017). Another administrative problem mentioned in multiple publications is the lack of a billing code for reimbursement of nitrous oxide as an analgesic (Illuzzi et al., 2018; Migliaccio et al., 2017; Pinyan et al., 2017).

Supporting Framework

The supporting framework used for this project was the Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice. The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice is a framework developed by the

University of Iowa in 1994 to facilitate knowledge translation to evidence-based practice (Titler et al., 2001; Doody & Doody, 2011). Since its initial development, the Iowa Model has been revised and revalidated to take into consideration the advancements in evidence-based practice in healthcare (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Implementing evidence-based practice change within hospital facilities is an arduous task that requires the coordination of multiple interdisciplinary teams. Providing a pathway by utilizing this model for protocol implementation helps healthcare providers facilitate the process by allowing them to anticipate barriers that may become evident throughout the implementation process. In addition, providing a more focused pathway limits wasting fiscal and personnel resources during project implementation (Titler et al., 2001; Doody & Doody, 2011). Therefore, the Iowa model creates a straightforward and easily understandable method to accomplish this. This model has been demonstrated to be successful in guiding the implementation of many quality improvement projects for protocol implementation. For example, Bergstrom (2011) described how the Iowa framework could assist in creating a protocol to provide skincare to patients affected by radiation. Specifically, the Iowa model has even been utilized by nursing staff for the implementation of nitrous oxide for labor analgesia at a 129-bed regional hospital in the midwest (Rivas et al, 2018). (See Appendix A for visual presentation of the Revised Iowa Model)

The Iowa Model consists of a seven-step pathway with several decision points integrated into the framework to help the user decide on whether to continue through a path or reevaluate (Titler et al., 2001). The first step consists of creating a topic based on identified triggering issues/opportunities. For this project, leadership from KP SCAL indicated an increased demand for less invasive analgesic methods, specifically nitrous oxide, requested by parturients receiving

obstetrical care. Thus, developing a clinical reference related to nitrous oxide use for labor anesthesia was deemed to be a priority for the institution.

The second step is generating a purpose statement for the identified topic. The purpose of this project was to create reference material on nitrous oxide for labor-management with the intent to improve the labor experience and parturient satisfaction by facilitating the implementation of nitrous oxide for labor management. The first decision point in the Iowa model creates the initial point of re-evaluation in which it must be determined whether this clinical problem is indeed a priority for the organization. This project aligns with Kaiser Permanente's mission to improve patient satisfaction by providing patient-centered care through the incorporation of nitrous oxide as an adjunct for labor pain management.

The third step requires the formation of an interdisciplinary team (Titler et al., 2001). Establishing a diverse team of healthcare professionals that range from hospital administration to obstetrical nurses is critical for successful implementation. The mixture of ideas can create a unique perspective on the problem at hand while examining the practicality of various interventions (Doody & Doody, 2011). The team for this project will consist of three Doctor of Nursing Practice, nurse anesthesia students, a Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetist (CRNA), and a board-certified Southern California Permanente Medical Group (SCPMG) physician.

The next two steps in the Iowa model involve the retrieval and grading of evidence obtained on the topic (Titler et al., 2001). A comprehensive literature search was conducted as described in the "Search Methods" section of this paper, and the studies were analyzed for relevance and quality. Based on the synthesis of the review of literature, sufficient evidence supports the implementation of nitrous oxide as an effective labor analgesia adjunct.

The fifth step consists of developing a clinical reference (Titler et al., 2001). Approval of the product is a crucial step in the Iowa model as it helps to identify issues with the content, implementation, and rollout of the project to multiple clinical settings (Cullen et al., 2018). The product will be the developed Nitrous Oxide for Labor Clinical Reference based on a review of the literature. The project's team of stakeholders will plan out the approval process including development of the clinical reference, communication with SCPMG, setting overall goals, and methods to measure goals.

The sixth step of the model addresses the integration and sustainment of the adopted practice change (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The continuation of measuring outcomes, evaluating the results of the change, and reeducating staff will assist in a smooth initiation of nitrous oxide for labor once facilities are ready to implement this intervention. The final step is to disseminate results, which will be done through the publication of the SCPMG regionally approved clinical reference on the KP Clinical Library website. The results determining the effectiveness of the clinical reference will be communicated during staff meetings for key stakeholders.

Methods

The purpose of this evidence-based clinical reference development project is to improve the laboring experience within KP SCAL facilities by offering nitrous oxide as an adjunct for labor analgesia. The specific aims of our project consist of developing a SCPMG regionally approved clinical reference for KP SCAL obstetrical staff on the use of nitrous oxide during labor. Clinical references provide education and guidance to healthcare providers regarding the appropriate use of the intervention.

Design and Target Audience

The creation of a clinical reference document is one of the primary building blocks for the future implementation of nitrous oxide for a labor analgesia program. The clinical reference contains vital information surrounding the use of nitrous oxide during labor, as well as, self-administration practices, safety and occupational hazards and parturient contraindications. Following the rigorous approval process, the clinical reference will be published on the KP SCAL Clinical Library Intranet website. Any KP SCAL employee interested in receiving further education on the use of nitrous oxide for labor analgesia will have access to this document. It is our goal to provide an educational reference that will help guide KP SCAL obstetrical staff towards developing a protocol for the future implementation of nitrous oxide for labor analgesia.

Ethical Issues

Permission to proceed with our creation of KP clinical reference project was granted by the KP SCAL administration. Federal regulations require IRB approval with special considerations when it involves vulnerable populations such as an obstetrical patient. The proposal was submitted to the Institutional Review Boards (IRB) of California State University-

Fullerton and KP SCAL Regional Administration. Due to the minimal risk to patients and nurses, it was exempt from full IRB review.

Publication of the Clinical Reference

The following section outlines the steps in which the clinical reference for nitrous oxide self-administration for labor analgesia will be developed. Currently, there is no clinical reference in place to guide staff on the self-administration of nitrous oxide as a labor analgesic in KP SCAL facilities. The utilization of nitrous oxide self-administration will become part of KP SCAL facilities in the near future due to patient demand for alternate options of labor analgesia by Kaiser Permanente facilities.

Step 1: Clinical Reference Initial Approval

Qualifications to become a regionally approved clinical reference requires approval by SCPMG Chiefs of Service or regional committees of all specialties expected to use it. This project will require initial approval and sponsorship from a board-certified SCPMG physician in order to initiate steps to allow development and publication of the proposed clinical reference on the KP Clinical Library. Our team identified Audrey Yen, an obstetric anesthesiologist, as our board-certified SCPMG physician sponsor. Publication will not be allowed unless there is documentation of approval from the directors of KP guideline management team. This publication will allow all KP SCAL healthcare employees to easily access the KP clinical reference on the Clinical Library website once nitrous oxide becomes available in KP SCAL facilities.

Step 2: Development of Clinical Reference

A literature review was performed focusing on nitrous oxide utilization during labor pain. Identifying its efficacy, safety concerns, contraindications, facilitators and barriers to

implementing nitrous oxide in the obstetric setting. The specifics of the proposed clinical reference and its development was discussed with our physician sponsor to gain their input and support. The KP clinical reference was developed according to the KP SCAL clinical reference policy and formatting (See Appendix B for details). Our Nitrous Oxide for Labor Analgesia Clinical Reference can be viewed in Appendix C.

Step 3: Submission and Review of Clinical Reference

The newly developed clinical reference should be submitted to the SCPMG Assistant Medical Director for Quality and Clinical Analysis, Quality and Risk Management, as well as SCPMG Guidelines Management Team for quality review of content. This process will include a review by these KP teams to determine clarity, relevance, and consistency with SCPMG regional clinical quality goals and initiatives. The clinical reference will be returned with suggestions for revisions if quality review standards are not deemed adequate for a clinical reference.

Step 4: Final Approval and Renewal

A final approval of the clinical reference by the SCPMG Assistant Medical Director for Quality and Clinical Analysis is required prior to publication on the KP Clinical Library. Once published, this clinical reference must be updated at least every two years to maintain up-to-date content. Failure to update content within a two-year period will result in the removal of the clinical reference from the KP Clinical Library.

Evaluation

As discussed in the “Methods” section of this proposal, the development of an SCPMG regionally approved clinical reference involves numerous steps of evaluation. The goal for this project is achieved through the acceptance of the clinical reference for publication on the KP SCAL Clinical Library website. Once published, the contents of the clinical reference should be

taken to be evaluated for accuracy every two years. Failure to do so will result in the retirement of the clinical reference. SCPMG Chiefs of Service and/or regional committees of all specialties are required to approve updates.

Although measuring the efficacy of the clinical reference is beyond the scope of this project, there are plans for evaluation of its effectiveness after publication. This clinical reference is intended to be readily available for the frontline staff, who are providing nitrous to laboring women. Thus, laying the groundwork for the future implementation of a nitrous oxide protocol and supplementing education on the intervention. Therefore, education on and implementation of the nitrous oxide during labor should occur before assessing the efficacy of the clinical reference. Methods of evaluation for the clinical reference will involve KP SCAL obstetrical staff and the information technology (IT) department. Obstetrical staff input will come from nitrous oxide for labor analgesia education evaluations. These evaluations will include questions regarding the usefulness, ease of access, and clarity of the clinical reference. Secondly, the IT department will track the number of visits to the Nitrous Oxide for Labor Analgesia Clinical Reference. These evaluation methods will determine the effectiveness of the Nitrous Oxide for Labor Analgesia Clinical Reference in clinical practice.

Results

The purpose of this clinical reference was to have a concise reference readily available for staff members of any KP SCAL facility involved in the direct care of nitrous oxide administration to laboring women (See Appendix C to see pending clinical reference). Our project evaluation would consist of the efficiency and convenience of the clinical reference to KP obstetrical staff. This outcome would only be feasible after publication and once a KP SCAL facility initiates nitrous oxide administration within their facilities. Therefore, our clinical reference was created with the hopes of eventually supporting the implementation as an alternative option for labor pain management at KP SCAL facilities. However, given the current events of COVID-19 the option of offering nitrous oxide to laboring mothers at KP SCAL facilities was indefinitely paused due to concerns regarding its method of administration and aerosolization. Currently given the extent of COVID-19 pandemic there is insufficient information regarding cleaning, filtering, and potential for aerosolization associated with nitrous oxide utilized for labor (Arnolds & Scavone, 2020). Unfortunately offering this modality for labor management would not be available until after it can be deemed a safe alternative method. At present, most journal of obstetrics and gynecology articles advocate eliminating nitrous oxide use during COVID-19 pandemic (Boelig et al., 2020; Ring et al. 2020).

Once KP SCAL facilities to determine that when it is safe and appropriate to implement this intervention, our clinical reference will allow staff to have a concise method of identifying steps necessary in screening, administration, and management of nitrous oxide. The clinical reference created is succinct, however, it can be utilized by educational staff members to construct a further detailed guideline and administration protocol that are specific to each KP SCAL facility. Key personnel for this project would be determined once it is safe to proceed with

this type of labor option. Utilizing an interdisciplinary team approach, the anesthesia provider would initially guide and educate obstetrical staff in the safe practices of nitrous oxide administration. Once the intervention is established, the lead role would transition to an obstetrical nurse to maintain this practice change. In addition, once sufficient evidence is available regarding best practices of nitrous oxide administration during COVID-19 pandemic, modifications to the clinical reference can then be made to adhere to safe practices.

Discussion

The project's goal was to develop and submit an SCPMG regionally approved clinical reference to KP SCAL Clinical Library. Once we had created our clinical reference, it was necessary to identify a sponsor who would evaluate the clinical reference before submission to SCPMG Assistant Medical Director for Quality and Clinical Analysis. This intervention's implementation and success are contingent on specific facilitators (Physician sponsor, SCPMG Assistant Medical Director, Quality and Risk Management team, SCPMG Guidelines Management Team). However, due to current events of the novel coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) and a necessity for KP SCAL regional resources to be directed elsewhere, there were challenges in identifying a different sponsor than initially planned to evaluate and accept the clinical reference for submission. Without having all facilitators of concern available, it was difficult to ensure full publication in the KP SCAL clinical library.

Despite expected facilitators becoming barriers, our obstetric clinical rotation became an unanticipated facilitator. During this rotation, a group member discovered a physician, Dr. Yen, who is an advocate for nitrous oxide as a labor analgesic. Later, Dr. Yen agreed to be the physician sponsor for our clinical reference. Despite finding a sponsor, publication of the Nitrous Oxide for Labor Analgesia Clinical Reference has halted until further notice related to the risks of using nitrous oxide as a labor analgesic during the COVID-19 pandemic. A description of the project's practicality for future implementation and utilization of nitrous oxide for labor analgesia was proposed to pursue future publication. Therefore, once nitrous oxide can be offered at KP SCAL facilities, the clinical reference created will be ready to be evaluated, approved, and published. Once published, it will be able to be utilized by healthcare providers.

Conclusion

The utilization of nitrous oxide for labor analgesia is an important adjunct to offer to parturients as this provides alternative choices for the parturients labor experience, thereby improving satisfaction. The clinical reference is critical in addressing the knowledge deficit that exists among health care providers in a clear and concise manner lending confidence to the obstetrical team. Utilizing the steps of the Iowa framework assisted in the translation of evidence-based practice knowledge of nitrous oxide administration for parturients into a clinical reference. This pathway allowed our group to initially identify integral factors healthcare providers must understand prior to administration. Ultimately, this mitigates any inconsistencies that may occur with facility specific guideline creation. In addition, it allowed us to anticipate potential barriers that became apparent in our literature review such as a knowledge deficit among healthcare providers which allowed us to focus on addressing this in our project. Additional articles were published subsequent to writing our literature review, solidifying the benefits of offering nitrous oxide with no conflicting conclusions. However, current literature does not recommend the use of nitrous oxide administration in the setting of COVID-19 (Bauer et al., 2020; Boelig et al, 2020; Ring et al, 2020). As more concrete evidence becomes available regarding the safe administration practices and proper device sanitation, the clinical reference can be updated to mirror best practice standards and allow for this modality to be provided to parturients.

References

- Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality. (2012). Nitrous oxide for the management of labor pain. <https://effectivehealthcare.ahrq.gov/products/labor-nitrous-oxide/research>
- Anderson, D. (2011). A review of systemic opioids commonly used for labor pain relief. *Journal of Midwifery & Women's Health*, 56(3), 222-239. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1542-2011.2011.00061.x>
- Arnolds, D. E. & Scavone, B. M. (2020). Safety and utility of nitrous oxide for labor analgesia. *Anesthesia Patient Safety Foundation*. <https://www.apsf.org/article/safety-and-utility-of-nitrous-oxide-for-labor-analgesia/>
- Attanasio, L. B., Kozhimannil, K. B., Jou, J., McPherson, M. E., & Camann, W. (2015). Women's experiences with neuraxial labor analgesia in the listening to mothers II survey: A content analysis of open-ended responses. *Anesthesia and Analgesia*, 121(4), 974. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0000000000000546>
- Attanasio, L. B., McPherson, M. E., & Kozhimannil, K. B. (2014). Positive childbirth experiences in US hospitals: A mixed methods analysis. *Maternal and Child Health Journal*, 18(5), 1280-1290. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10995-013-1363-1>
- Bauer, M., Bernstein, K., Dinges, E., Delgado, C., El-Sharawi, N., Sultan, P., Mhyre, J., & Landau, R. (2020). Obstetric anesthesia during the coronavirus disease 2019 pandemic. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0000000000004856>
- Becker, D. E., & Rosenberg, M. (2008). Nitrous oxide and the inhalation anesthetics. *Anesthesia Progress*, 55(4), 124-131. <https://doi.org/10.2344/0003-3006-55.4.124>

- Bergstrom, K. (2011). Development of a radiation skin care protocol and algorithm using the Iowa model of evidence-based practice. *Clinical Journal of Oncology Nursing*, 15(6), 593-595. <https://doi.org/10.1188/11.CJON.593-595>
- Berlit, S., Tuschy, B., Brade, J., Mayer, J., Kehl, S., & Sütterlin, M. (2013). Effectiveness of nitrous oxide for postpartum perineal repair: A randomised controlled trial. *European Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 170(2), 329-332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejogrb.2013.06.025>
- Boelig, R. C., Manuck, T., Oliver, E. A., DiMascio, D., Saccone, G., Bellussi, F., & Berghella, V. M. (2020). Labor and delivery guidance for COVID-19. *American Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology MFM*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajogmf.2020.100110>
- Brownridge, P. (1995). The nature and consequences of childbirth pain. *European Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Reproductive Biology*, 59, S9-S15. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0028-2243\(95\)02058-Z](https://doi.org/10.1016/0028-2243(95)02058-Z)
- Buckwalter, K., Cullen, L., Hanrahan, K., Kleiber, C., Mccarthy, A., Rakel, B., Steelman, V., Tripp-Reimer, T., & Tucker, S. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 14(3), 175-182. <https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12223>
- Collins, M. (2015). A case report on the anxiolytic properties of nitrous oxide during labor. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing*, 44(1), 87-92. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1552-6909.12522>
- Collins, S., Fiore, A. T., Boudreau, J. A., & Hewer, I. (2018). Nitrous oxide for the management of labor analgesia. *American Association of Nurse Anesthetists Journal*, 86(1), 72-80.

- Collins, M. R., Starr, S. A., Bishop, J. T., Baysinger, C. L. (2012). Nitrous oxide for labor analgesia: Expanding analgesic options for women in the United States. *Reviews in Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 5(3-4), e126–e131. <https://doi.org/10.3909/riog0190>
- Cullen, L., Hanrahan, K., Farrington, M., DeBerg, J., Tucker, S., Kleiber, C. (2018). *Evidence-based practice in action: Comprehensive strategies, tools, and tips from the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics*. Sigma Theta Tau International.
- Dammer, U., Weiss, C., Raabe, E., Heimrich, J., Koch, M. C., Winkler, M., Faschingbauer, F., Beckermann, S., & Kehl, S. (2014). Introduction of inhaled nitrous oxide and oxygen for pain management during labour - Evaluation of patients' and midwives' satisfaction. *Geburtshilfe und Frauenheilkunde*, 74(7), 656–660. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0034-1368606>
- Declercq, E. R., Sakala, C., Corry, M. P., Applebaum, S., & Herrlich, A. (2014). Major survey findings of listening to mothers (SM) III: Pregnancy and birth: Report of the third National U.S. survey of women's childbearing experiences. *The Journal of Perinatal Education*, 23(1), 9–16. <https://doi.org/10.1891/1058-1243.23.1.9>
- Doody, C. M., & Doody, O. (2011). Introducing evidence into nursing practice: Using the IOWA model. *British Journal of Nursing*, 20(11), 661–664. <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjon.2011.20.11.661>
- Earhart, K. R., Cuff, R. D., Hebbar, L. F., Goodier, C., & Mateus Nino, J. (2019). Effect of labor analgesia on fetal heart tracing in term pregnancies: Nitrous oxide versus epidural. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 133(1), 105S-106S. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.AOG.0000558817.70612.fc>

- Emmanouil, D. E., & Quock, R. M. (2007). Advances in understanding the actions of nitrous oxide. *Anesthesia Progress*, 54(1), 9-18. [https://doi.org/10.2344/0003-3006\(2007\)54\[9:AIUTAO\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.2344/0003-3006(2007)54[9:AIUTAO]2.0.CO;2)
- Floris, L., & Irion, O. (2015). Association between anxiety and pain in the latent phase of labour upon admission to the maternity hospital: A prospective, descriptive study. *Journal of Health Psychology*, 20(4), 446-455. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1359105313502695>
- Garthus-Niegel, S., Knoph, C., Von Soest, T., Nielsen, C. S., & Eberhard-Gran, M. (2014). The role of labor pain and overall birth experience in the development of posttraumatic stress symptoms: A longitudinal cohort study. *Birth*, 41(1), 108-115. <https://doi.org/10.1111/birt.12093>
- Hellams, A., Sprague, T., Saldanha, C., & Archambault, M. (2018). Nitrous oxide for labor analgesia. *Journal of the American Academy of PAs*, 31(1), 41-44. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.JAA.0000527700.00698.8c>
- Houser, T., DeButy, K., & Beal, C. C. (2019). Implementation of an evidence-based practice change to offer nitrous oxide during labor. *Nursing for Women's Health*, 23(1), 11-20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nwh.2018.12.001>
- Illuzzi, J. L., Telfer, M. L., & Rubin, P. (2018). Nitrous oxide's revival in childbirth. *Contemporary OB/GYN*, 63(5), 7-11. <https://www.contemporaryobgyn.net/view/nitrous-oxides-revival-childbirth>
- Jones, L., Othman, M., Dowswell, T., Alfirevic, Z., Gates, S., Newburn, M., Jordan, S., Lavender, T., & Neilson, J. P. (2012). Pain management for women in labour: An overview of systematic reviews. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, (3). <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD009234.pub2>

- Lew, V., McKay, E., & Maze, M. (2018). Past, present, and future of nitrous oxide. *British Medical Bulletin*, 125(1), 103. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bmb/ldx050>
- Likis, F. E., Andrews, J. C., Collins, M. R., Lewis, R. M., Seroogy, J. J., Starr, S. A., Walden, R. R. & McPheeters, M. L. (2014). Nitrous oxide for the management of labor pain: A systematic review. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*, 118(1), 153-167. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0b013e3182a7f73c>
- Lowe, N. (2002). The nature of labor pain. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 186(5), S16-S24. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9378\(02\)70179-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9378(02)70179-8)
- Migliaccio, L., Lawton, R., Leeman, L., & Holbrook, A. (2017). Initiating intrapartum nitrous oxide in an academic hospital: Considerations and challenges. *Journal of Midwifery & Women's Health*, 62(3), 358-362. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jmwh.12635>
- Naddoni, D. B., Balakundi, S. K., & Assainar, K. K. (2016). The effect of nitrous oxide (Entonox) on labour. *International Journal of Reproduction Contraction, Obstetrics Gynecology*, 5, 835-9. <https://doi.org/10.18203/2320-1770.ijrcog20160594>
- Nodine, P. M., Collins, M. R., Wood, C. L., Anderson, J. L., Orlando, B. S., McNair, B. K., Mayer, D. C., Stein, D. J. (2020). Nitrous oxide use during labor: Satisfaction, adverse effects, and predictors of conversion to neuraxial analgesia. *Journal of Midwifery & Women's Health*, 65(3), 335-341. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jmwh.13124>
- Parsa, P., Saeedzadeh, N., Roshanaei, G., Shobeiri, F., & Hakemzadeh, F. (2017). The effect of Entonox on labour pain relief among nulliparous women: A randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research* 11(3), QC08. <https://doi.org/10.7860/JCDR/2017/21611.9362>

- Pasha, H., Basirat, Z., Hajahmadi, M., Bakhtiari, A., Faramarzi, M., & Salmalian, H. (2012). Maternal expectations and experiences of labor analgesia with nitrous oxide. *Iranian Red Crescent Medical Journal*, *14*(12), 792. <https://doi.org/10.5812/ircmj.3470>
- Pettersson, F. D., Hellgren, C., Nyberg, F., Åkerud, H., & Sundström-Poromaa, I. (2016). Depressed mood, anxiety, and the use of labor analgesia. *Archives of Women's Mental Health*, *19*(1), 11-16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00737-015-0572-6>
- Phillips, S.N., Fernando, R., & Girard, T. (2017). Parenteral opioid analgesia: Does it still have a role? *Best Practice & Research Clinical Anaesthesiology*, *31*(1), 3-14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpa.2017.02.002>
- Pinyan, T., Curlee, K., Keever, M., & Baldwin, K. M. (2017). A nurse-directed model for nitrous oxide use during labor. *MCN: The American Journal of Maternal/Child Nursing*, *42*(3), 160-165. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NMC.0000000000000336>
- Richardson, M. G., Lopez, B. M., & Baysinger, C. L. (2017a). Should nitrous oxide be used for laboring patients? *Anesthesiology Clinics*, *35* 125-143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anclin.2016.09.011>
- Richardson, M. G., Lopez, B. M., Baysinger, C. L., Shotwell, M. S., & Chestnut, D. H. (2017b). Nitrous oxide during labor: Maternal satisfaction does not depend exclusively on analgesic effectiveness. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*, *124*(2), 548-553. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0000000000001680>
- Richardson, M. G., Raymond, B. L., Baysinger, C. L., Kook, B. T., & Chestnut, D. H. (2019). A qualitative analysis of parturients' experiences using nitrous oxide for labor analgesia: It is not just about pain relief. *Birth*, *46*(1), 97-104. <https://doi.org/10.1111/birt.12374>

- Ring, L. E., Martinez, R., Bernstein, K., & Landau, R. (2020). What obstetricians should know about obstetric anesthesia during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Seminars in Perinatology*, 131, 7-15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.semperi.2020.151277>
- Rivas, C. L., Crenshaw, J. T., & Gilder, R. E. (2018). Use of nitrous oxide for labor and birth pain management. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic, & Neonatal Nursing* 47(3), S43-S44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jogn.2018.04.086>
- Rooks, J. P. (2011). Safety and Risks of Nitrous Oxide Labor Analgesia: A review. *Journal of Midwifery & Women's Health*, 56(6), 557-565. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1542-2011.2011.00122.x>
- Sanders, R. D., Weimann, J., & Maze, M. (2008). Biologic effects of nitrous oxide: A mechanistic and toxicologic review. *Anesthesiology: The Journal of the American Society of Anesthesiologists*, 109(4), 707-722. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ALN.0b013e3181870a17%J>
- Savage, S., & Ma, D. (2014). The neurotoxicity of nitrous oxide: The facts and "putative" mechanisms. *Brain Sciences*, 4(1), 73-90. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci4010073>
- Schrock, S. D., & Harraway-Smith, C. (2012). Labor analgesia. *American Family Physician*, 85(5). <https://www.aafp.org/afp/2012/0301/p447.pdf>
- Sheyklo, S. G., Hajebrahimi, S., Moosavi, A., Pournaghi-Azar, F., Azami-Aghdash, S., & Ghojzadeh, M. (2017). Effect of Entonox for pain management in labor: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Electronic Physician*, 9(12), 6002–6009. <https://doi.org/10.19082/6002>

- Smith, L. A., Burns, E., & Cuthbert, A. (2018). Parenteral opioids for maternal pain management in labour. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 6(6), CD007396.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD007396.pub3>
- Sng, B. L., & Sia, A. T. (2017). Maintenance of epidural labour analgesia: The old, the new and the future. *Best Practice & Research Clinical Anaesthesiology*, 31(1), 15-22.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpa.2017.01.002>
- Starr, S. A., & Baysinger, C. L. (2013). Inhaled nitrous oxide for labor analgesia. *Anesthesiology Clinics*, 31(3), 623-634. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anclin.2013.04.001>
- Titler, M. G., Kleiber, C., Steelman, V. J., Rakel, B. A., Budreau, G., Everett, L. Q., Buckwalter, K. C., Tripp-Reimer, T., & Goode, C. J. (2001). The Iowa model of evidence-based practice to promote quality care. *Critical Care Nursing Clinics of North America*, 13(4), 497-509. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0899-5885\(18\)30017-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0899-5885(18)30017-0)
- Vallejo, M. C., & Zakowski, M. I. (2019). Pro-con debate: Nitrous oxide for labor analgesia. *BioMed Research International*, 2019, 4618798. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/4618798>
- Van Der Kooy, J., Graaf, J. P., Kolder, Z. M., Witters, K. D., Fitzpatrick, E., Duvekot, J., Dons-Sinke, I. J. J., Steegers, E. A. P. Bonsel, G. J. (2012). A newly developed scavenging system for administration of nitrous oxide during labour: Safe occupational use. *Acta Anaesthesiologica Scandinavica*, 56(7), 920-925. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1399-6576.2012.02668.x>
- Vedam, S., Stoll, K., Taiwo, T. K., Rubashkin, N., Cheyney, M., Strauss, N., McLemore, M., Cadena, M., Nethery, E., Rushton, E., Schummers, L., & Declercq, E. (2019). The giving voice to mothers study: Inequity and mistreatment during pregnancy and childbirth in the

United States. *Reproductive Health*, 16(1), 77. [https://doi.org/10.1186/s12978-019-0729-](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12978-019-0729-2)

2

Wrońska-Nofer, T., Nofer, J., Jajte, J., Dziubałtowska, E., Szymczak, W., Krajewski, W., Wasowicz, W., & Rydzyński, K. (2012). Oxidative DNA damage and oxidative stress in subjects occupationally exposed to nitrous oxide (N₂O). *Mutation Research - Fundamental and Molecular Mechanisms of Mutagenesis*, 731(1-2), 58-63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mrfmmm.2011.10.010>

Zanardo, V., Volpe, F., Parotto, M., Giiberti, L., Selmin, A., & Straface, G. (2018). Nitrous oxide labor analgesia and pain relief memory in breastfeeding women. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine*, 31(24), 3243–3248. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14767058.2017.1368077>

APPENDIX A

Iowa Model Framework

The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

APPENDIX B

Regionally Approved Clinical Reference Template

CLINICAL REFERENCE | SCAL
JANUARY 2018

Southern California Policy

SCPMG REGIONALLY APPROVED CLINICAL REFERENCES

- **Definition.** A "Regionally Approved Clinical Reference" is a document offering clinical education and guidance to practitioners related to specific medical conditions or the use of new medical technologies in patient care. Clinical References are acceptable as reference documents, but they generally do not meet the evidence standards or evaluation requirements defined for an evidence-based clinical practice guideline (see Southern California Policy for Evidence-Based Clinical Practice Guidelines).
- **Sponsorship.** All Regionally Approved Clinical References must be sponsored by a clinical group (e.g., Chiefs of Service, Regional Specialty Committee, clinical team, etc.), with responsibility for primary ownership and content oversight delegated to at least one or more board-certified SCPMG physicians. While Clinical Reference development teams may include nonphysician clinicians (e.g., physician assistants, nurse practitioners, health educators, etc.), at least one board-certified SCPMG physician must be listed as a primary contact for oversight of content.
- **Development Methodology.** In the development of a Clinical Reference, practitioners rely primarily on personal knowledge, clinical experience, judgment and expert consensus. Developers of Clinical References may selectively review or refer to the medical literature, but Clinical Reference development does not typically include nor require an explicit systematic search, critical appraisal and summary of the evidence that is necessary to meet the requirements for designation as a Southern California Regional Evidence-Based Clinical Practice Guideline.
- **Approval Requirements:** To qualify as a "Regionally Approved Clinical Reference," all content **must be approved by the relevant Southern California Permanente Medical Group (SCPMG) Chiefs of Service and/or Regional Committees of all specialties expected to be involved in its use and/or implementation.** Clinical References will not be published without documentation of approval from these groups.

In addition, prior to publication, a quality review of the content of each Clinical Reference is conducted by the SCPMG Assistant Medical Directors for Quality & Clinical Analysis and Quality & Risk Management, as well as a subgroup of members of the SCPMG Guidelines Management Team, to ensure clinical relevance, clarity and currency of content, as well as consistency with SCPMG regional clinical quality goals and initiatives. Clinical References that do not meet quality review standards are returned to the developers with comments and suggestions for revisions.

Final approval of all Clinical References by the SCPMG Assistant Medical Director for Quality & Clinical Analysis is required for publication on the Clinical Library.

- **Updating of Clinical References.** All Regionally Approved Clinical References **must be updated at least every two years.** This not only maintains the currency of the content, but it is also a requirement for publication on the Kaiser Permanente Southern California Clinical Library website. The SCPMG Evidence-Based Medicine (EBM) Services Unit contacts the authors of all Clinical References via e-mail approximately every 18 months to request that the content be updated. Substantive revisions to existing Clinical Reference content must be approved by the relevant SCPMG Chiefs of Service and/or Regional Committees of all specialties involved in its use and/or implementation. If the content is not updated within the designated two-year period, the Clinical Reference is retired and removed from the intranet.
 - **Intent.** The content in SCPMG Regionally Approved Clinical References is not intended to be used as standards for utilization management or determination of benefits coverage. SCPMG clinicians are responsible for applying recommendations to the specific clinical characteristics of each patient. In all clinical situations, SCPMG physicians have authority and autonomy in planning and directing the care of patients.
-

HOW TO SUBMIT CLINICAL REFERENCES FOR PUBLICATION

Organize the content as described in the **Format and Content** box (see instructions below). *NOTE: Writing, editing, evidence review, and/or formatting must be done by the group responsible for development of the Clinical Reference. All Clinical References may be subject to editing to meet format and content standards; however, it is the responsibility of the content developers to submit documents in the required format. Submission of a Clinical Reference does not guarantee that it will be published on the KPSC Clinical library intranet website.*

The SCPMG Evidence-Based Medicine (EBM) Services Unit coordinates the publication of all SCPMG regionally approved Clinical References on the KPSC Clinical Library website. Submit the Clinical Reference in the described format by e-mail to: Stephanie.D.Goldman@kp.org. If you have questions about the submission process, please e-mail or call Stephanie Goldman at tie-line 8-335-7904 or direct at (626) 405-7904. **Please submit only the final, approved versions of your specialty group's Clinical Reference for consideration for publication.**

HOW TO FORMAT CLINICAL REFERENCES FOR PUBLICATION*

1. **TITLE** (Please be specific and brief)

Example: **Alcohol Screening and Brief Intervention in Adults**

2. **APPROVAL DATE** (Please provide month and year in which the content was approved by the relevant stakeholder groups.)
3. **CONTACT Information** (Please provide information for at least one board-certified physician contact.)

Name	Name
Title	Title
Specialty (e.g., Endocrinology, Neurology, Ob/Gyn, etc.)	Specialty (e.g., Endocrinology, Neurology, Ob/Gyn, etc.)
Medical Center/Medical Office	Medical Center/Medical Office
e-mail address	e-mail address

4. **CONTENT** (Please use the standard section headings indicated below.)

BACKGROUND

Include a brief statement of the topic and scope, including target population to which the Clinical Reference applies (both patients and providers), the nature or magnitude of the problem addressed by the Clinical Reference, and the regional groups that have approved the Clinical Reference.

RECOMMENDATION

Text of Clinical Reference educational information and/or guidance. Emphasize key information with a bullet and/or bold text. Limit the content to key information and brief explanatory text. Please use complete sentences and define any acronyms used in the document. If an algorithm is included, it should specifically focus on the information in the Clinical Reference, and be referred to in the narrative text. Algorithms/flowcharts submitted as stand-alone content without accompanying explanatory text will be returned to the developers for supporting text.

RATIONALE

Description of the scientific and/or expert consensus basis of the Clinical Reference.

TECHNICAL NOTES

Key definitions or additional information that helps explain and/or implement the Clinical Reference.

SOURCES

Bibliography – please format citations in alphabetical order in the style used by the *New England Journal of Medicine*. Examples:

Cummings SR, Bates D, Black DM. Clinical Use of Bone Densitometry: A Scientific Review. *JAMA*. 2002;288(15):1889-97.

Nelson HD, Helfand M, Woolf SH, Allan JD. Screening for Postmenopausal Osteoporosis: A Summary of the Evidence. *Ann Intern Med*. 2002;137(6):529-541.

*Clinical References submitted for publication on the KPSC Clinical Library website that do not follow this format will be returned to the developers for reformatting.

*Clinical References submitted for publication on the KPSC Clinical Library website that do not follow this format will be returned to the developers for reformatting.

This guideline is intended to assist physicians in the evaluation of women age 18 and older for reduction mammoplasty. The recommendations have been approved by the Chiefs of Plastic Surgery, in consultation with plastic surgeons within their respective medical centers.

ABOUT THIS RESOURCE

First Issued: 01-1995

Last Reviewed/Revised: 01-2018

Printable Version: [Southern California Policy](#)

APPENDIX C

Nitrous Oxide for Labor Management Clinical Reference

A. Nitrous Oxide as a Labor Analgesia

B. Approval Date: MM/DD/YYYY

C. Contact Information:

- a. Name: Jennifer Thompson, DNP, CRNA
- b. Title: Academic & Clinical Instructor
- c. Specialty: Anesthesia
- d. Medical Center/Office: Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia
- e. E-mail address: Jen.L.Thompson@kp.org

D. Content (Required headings listed below)

a. **Background**

i. Nitrous Oxide as a Labor analgesic:

The use of nitrous oxide is one strategy that has been suggested to alleviate labor pain and reduce anxiety while maintaining parturient's autonomy. In the U.S., high concentrations of nitrous oxide were widely used for labor during the 1950s and 1960s but faded from practice with the emergence of neuraxial/regional anesthesia (Collins et al., 2018). In 2012, self-administering nitrous oxide devices were approved by the Food and Drug Administration for labor-management at a maximum concentration of a 50/50 gaseous mixture of nitrous oxide and oxygen (Collins, 2015; Collins et al., 2012; Pinyan et al., 2017). At this low concentration nitrous oxide works as a safe anxiolytic and analgesic. However, it is not a strong analgesic, and therefore is not intended to provide equivalent analgesia when compared to an epidural. Despite this, women have reported diminished pain and less anxiety when using nitrous oxide throughout the different stages of labor (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, 2012; Likis et al., 2014; Richardson et al., 2019).

ii. Mechanism of Action:

The mechanism of action is multifactorial and is not entirely understood. At high concentrations, greater than 50%, it is believed that nitrous oxide produces anesthetic effects predominantly by inhibition of N-methyl-D-aspartate excitatory glutamate receptors in the brain. At subanesthetic concentrations, 30% to 50%, analgesic and anxiolytic effects without unconsciousness are demonstrated. These effects enable the parturient to feel a sense of detachment and a decrease in pain perception yet, still being aware that the pain is present (Hellams et al., 2018; Illuzzi et al., 2018).

iii. Indications:

- Assist in the management of pain and/or anxiety related to the labor and delivery process
 - Including: perineal repair or manual removal of the placenta

iv. Efficacy:

Labor pain is subjective and individualized to each parturient. Although evidence suggests nitrous oxide as being a weak analgesic when administered at subanesthetic doses, additional effects such as anxiolysis and the ability of self-administration provides a positive birth experience in the laboring woman.

Overall, studies regarding the efficacy of nitrous oxide for the management of labor pain are limited, but still, demonstrate its weak analgesic effect. Positive outcomes concerning the efficacy of pain relief in studies appear to be based on nitrous oxide's ability to meet the parturient's preconceived goals for labor rather than completely abolishing pain (Richardson et al., 2017a).

Evidence suggests that nitrous oxide may not be effective in every case of labor pain management; nevertheless, it may be more effective in women desiring a more natural birthing experience and less invasive pain management strategies (Berlit et al., 2013; Richardson et al., 2017a).

Important factors with nitrous oxide self-administration such as degree of mobility and autonomy promote a greater degree of empowerment and result in improved parturient satisfaction.

Rather than being seen as a replacement for epidurals, nitrous oxide can be recognized as a substitute to utilizing narcotics, an adjunct to nonpharmacologic methods of labor-management, or assist with the transition to neuraxial anesthesia.

b. Recommendation

i. Screening:

- Laboring/Scheduled induction
- No documented diagnosis or suspicion of Vitamin B12 deficiency
- Oxygenation > 95% on room air
- Category 1 or II fetal heart rate trace
- No evidence of increased intracranial pressure, intraocular pressure, or pulmonary hypertension
- No diagnosis or suspicion of pneumothorax or bowel obstruction
- History of intraocular surgery using intraocular gas (4-6 weeks)
- No evidence of recent alcohol or illegal drug use
- Contraindications:
 - i. Patients inability to self-administer via facemask
 - ii. Taking B12 supplementation
 - iii. Decreased Vitamin B12 functioning
 - Ex. Crohn's disease, celiac disease, gluten intolerance, pernicious anemia, history of bariatric surgery, and/or a strict vegan diet

- iv. Category III fetal heart rate tracing
- v. Head trauma within the last 2 weeks
- Relative contraindications:
 - i. SBP consistently <100mmHg
 - ii. Category II fetal heart rate tracing
 - iii. Patient having received IV opioids within the last 2 hours (consult with obstetric anesthesia before administering nitrous oxide)
(Houser et al., 2019)
- ii. Administration of Nitrous Oxide:
 - Initial order placed by obstetrical provider on Labor & Delivery Unit.
 - Setup:
 - Inspect equipment
 - Sign out nitrous oxide equipment in log book (log back in after use of equipment)
 - Sign out medication from the pyxis under patient's name
 - Registered nurse (RN) must be present on initial administration of nitrous oxide analgesia until the patient demonstrates competency and to assess for patient status changes.
 - Preparation:
 - Assess maternal vital signs (q 5 min x 1, 15 min x 4, 30 min x 2, then per standing order)
 - IV access
 - Provide patient education
 - Patient Education:
 - Possible adverse effects
 - i. Nausea/vomiting, dry mouth, altered sense of taste and smell, Drowsiness, dizziness, lightheaded, vertigo, disorientation, dysphoria, amnesia, tingling of fingers/toes
 - Mandatory assistance out of bed once nitrous oxide has been started
 - Self administration: properly creating a seal with facemask, timing of breath for most effect (See "Administration"), and adequately exhaling back into mask
 - Only the parturient is permitted to hold the face mask over her face and should not receive assistance if she is too drowsy to achieve this task independently
 - Administration:

- Nitronox apparatus utilizes a blender device that combines nitrous oxide and oxygen sources to be delivered at a fixed concentration of 50% nitrous oxide
- The nitrous oxide is delivered via a handheld face mask.
- A tight seal is created as the parturient places the mask over the nose and mouth. Upon inhalation, a negative pressure demand valve is triggered, releasing the blend of gases to the patient. Rapid uptake of the gas produces maximum analgesic effectiveness within 30 to 50 seconds.
- Intermittent inhalation in practice is known as the most superior method of self-administration. Instruct parturient to initiate inhalation approximately 30 seconds before the onset of contractions, this method allows for the parturient to receive maximum analgesic effectiveness during the peak of uterine contraction.
- After exhaling into the mask, the patient may remove the mask when not experiencing contractions and breath normally.
- Following the cessation of contraction, the parturient is instructed to exhale back into the mask so that the gaseous waste is eliminated via the scavenging system.
- If at any point during self-administration the parturient becomes sedated or too drowsy to hold the mask independently, the flow of gas terminates as there is no longer a tight mask seal. Nitrous oxide has a fast offset and is quickly eliminated within minutes through exhalation. Once the parturient recovers and is able to independently place the mask over her face, the inhalational force will, once again, trigger the release of gas.

c. Rationale

i. Safety:

Nitrous oxide use for labor analgesia demonstrates minimal toxicity and depression of the cardiovascular system in laboring women (Rooks, 2011).

Nitrous oxide crosses the placenta; however, it is not metabolized in fetal or maternal tissue, therefore, central nervous system and respiratory depression are not seen in neonates after birth due to rapid elimination with the initiation of respiration (Collins et al., 2018).

Studies demonstrate no effect on Apgar and neurobehavioral scores of neonates, as well as, fetal heart rate from its utilization (Earhart et al., 2019; Likis et al. 2014; Rooks, 2011).

U.S. standard exposure limit for healthcare workers recommended by the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health defines a set 8 hour limit of 25 parts per million (Vallejo & Zakowski, 2019)

At present, there is no evidence connecting occupational exposure of self-administered nitrous oxide utilized in the labor setting to reproductive risk of healthcare workers when scavenging equipment is utilized appropriately. Justifications for increased occupational exposure are demonstrated to be due to mothers failing to exhale back into the mask, poor mask fit, and improper ventilation systems on units (Vallejo & Zakowski, 2019; Van Der Kooy, 2012; Rooks, 2011).

ii. Women's satisfaction:

The laboring process is a complex and subjective experience that is highly individualized (Lowe, 2002). Therefore, a variety of approaches to promote comfort and pain are necessary to improve the labor experience. At a concentration of 50/50, parturients are able to maintain alertness, as well as sustain motor and sensory function, while experiencing a diminished perception of pain, improved relaxation and decreased stress levels (Hellams et al., 2018; Illuzzi et al., 2018). All of these factors contribute to women having more sense of control over their laboring experience resulting in an increase in overall patient satisfaction.

Multiple studies revealed high satisfaction with the utilization of nitrous oxide (Houser et al., 2019; Richardson et al., 2017b; Richardson et al., 2019; Rivas et al., 2018; Zanardo et al., 2018). Richardson et al. (2017b) identified that parturients who received solely nitrous oxide for labor analgesia reported high overall satisfaction scores when compared to those receiving only neuraxial analgesia (OR 2.5; 95% CI 1.4-4.6; P= 0.002).

d. Technical Notes

i. Details about the Nitronix device:

- The Nitronox machine combines separate nitrous oxide and oxygen sources in a blender device. It delivers a preset concentration of 50% nitrous oxide and 50% oxygen.
- FDA approved device for obstetrical services in the US
- The Nitronox machine can use both wall and e-cylinder tank sources of nitrous oxide and oxygen.

- Contains a scavenger unit that actively suctions exhaled gases for evacuation via a standard wall suction port
- Demand valve limits the high pressure gas flow to occur only during active inhalation. This allows for deep breaths to be timed specifically to the parturients' contractions
- Demand valve also prevents leakage of nitrous oxide into the environment when the parturient is not using the device in between contractions.

e. Sources

- i. Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (2012). Nitrous oxide for the management of labor pain. <https://effectivehealthcare.ahrq.gov/products/labor-nitrous-oxide/research>
- ii. Berlit, S., Tuschy, B., Brade, J., Mayer, J., Kehl, S., & Sütterlin, M. (2013). Effectiveness of nitrous oxide for postpartum perineal repair: A randomised controlled trial. *European Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 170(2), 329-332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejogrb.2013.06.025>
- iii. Collins, M. (2015). A case report on the anxiolytic properties of nitrous oxide during labor. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing*, 44(1), 87-92. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1552-6909.12522>
- iv. Collins, S., Fiore, A. T., Boudreau, J. A., & Hewer, I. (2018). Nitrous oxide for the management of labor analgesia. *AANA Journal*, 86(1), 72-80.
- v. Collins, M. R., Starr, S. A., Bishop, J. T., Baysinger, C. L. (2012). Nitrous oxide for labor analgesia: Expanding analgesic options for women in the United States. *Reviews in Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 5(3-4), e126–e131. <https://doi.org/10.3909/riog0190>
- vi. Earhart, K. R., Cuff, R. D., Hebbar, L. F., Goodier, C., & Mateus Nino, J. (2019). Effect of labor analgesia on fetal heart tracing in term pregnancies: Nitrous oxide versus epidural. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 133(1), 105S-106S. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.AOG.0000558817.70612.fc>
- vii. Hellams, A., Sprague, T., Saldanha, C., & Archambault, M. (2018). Nitrous oxide for labor analgesia. *Journal of the American Academy of PAs*, 31(1), 41-44. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.JAA.0000527700.00698.8c>
- viii. Houser, T., DeButy, K., & Beal, C. C. (2019). Implementation of an evidence-based practice change to offer nitrous oxide during labor. *Nursing for Women's Health*, 23(1), 11-20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nwh.2018.12.001>
- ix. Illuzzi, J. L., Telfer, M. L., & Rubin, P. (2018). Nitrous oxide's revival in childbirth. *Contemporary OB/GYN*, 63(5), 7-11.
- x. Likis, F. E., Andrews, J. C., Collins, M. R., Lewis, R. M., Seroogy, J. J., Starr, S. A., Walden, R. R. & McPheeters, M. L. (2014). Nitrous oxide for the management of labor pain: A systematic review. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*, 118(1), 153-167. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0b013e3182a7f73c>
- xi. Lowe, N. (2002). The nature of labor pain. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 186(5), S16-S24. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9378\(02\)70179-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9378(02)70179-8)
- xii. Pinyan, T., Curlee, K., Keever, M., & Baldwin, K. M. (2017). A nurse-directed model for nitrous oxide use during labor. *MCN: The American Journal of Maternal/Child Nursing*, 42(3), 160-165. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NMC.0000000000000336>

- xiii. Richardson, M. G., Lopez, B. M., & Baysinger, C. L. (2017a). Should nitrous oxide be used for laboring patients? *Anesthesiology Clinics*, 35 125-143.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anclin.2016.09.011>
- xiv. Richardson, M. G., Lopez, B. M., Baysinger, C. L., Shotwell, M. S., & Chestnut, D. H. (2017b). Nitrous oxide during labor: Maternal satisfaction does not depend exclusively on analgesic effectiveness. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*, 124(2), 548-553.
<https://doi.org/10.1213 /ANE.0000000000001680>
- xv. Richardson, M. G., Raymond, B. L., Baysinger, C. L., Kook, B. T., & Chestnut, D. H. (2019). A qualitative analysis of parturients' experiences using nitrous oxide for labor analgesia: It is not just about pain relief. *Birth*, 46(1), 97-104.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/birt.12374>
- xvi. Rivas, C. L., Crenshaw, J. T., & Gilder, R. E. (2018). Use of nitrous oxide for labor and birth pain management. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic, & Neonatal Nursing* 47(3), S43-S44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jogn.2018.04.086>
- xvii. Rooks, J. P. (2011). Safety and risks of nitrous oxide labor analgesia: A review. *Journal of Midwifery & Women's Health*, 56(6), 557-565. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1542-2011.2011.00122.x>
- xviii. Vallejo, M. C., & Zakowski, M. I. (2019). Pro-con debate: Nitrous oxide for labor analgesia. *BioMed Research International*, 2019, 4618798.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/4618798>
- xix. Van Der Kooy, J., Graaf, J. P., Kolder, Z. M., Witters, K. D., Fitzpatrick, E., Duvekot, J., Dons-Sinke, I. J. J., Steegers, E. A. P. Bonsel, G. J. (2012). A newly developed scavenging system for administration of nitrous oxide during labour: Safe occupational use. *Acta Anaesthesiologica Scandinavica*, 56(7), 920-925.
<http://doi.org/10.1111/j.1399-6576.2012.02668.x>
- xx. Zano, V., Volpe, F., Parotto, M., Giuberti, L., Selmin, A., & Straface, G. (2018). Nitrous oxide labor analgesia and pain relief memory in breastfeeding women. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine: The Official Journal of the European Association of Perinatal Medicine, the Federation of Asia and Oceania Perinatal Societies, the International Society of Perinatal Obstetricians*, 31(24), 3243-3248.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14767058.2017.1368077>